

Optimization and characterization of extracted coffee oil obtained by supercritical CO₂ of spent coffee ground

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Abstract (250-300 words):

Spent coffee grounds (SCGs) are one of the most massive wastes from coffee processing and consumption worldwide. Although SCGs have a high content of carbohydrates, fatty acids and polyphenols, SCGs are usually valorized energetically or discarded, losing all these value-added compounds for the cosmetics industry. An option that is gaining many followers is to extract coffee oils containing these residues with supercritical CO₂ (scCO₂), since it is a method that does not damage the environment as much as other extractions and does not destroy the most valuable compounds. In the framework of the HOOP project, SCGs were collected from the Madaloki restaurant in the city of Kozani, Western Macedonia, and an oil fraction was extracted from this biowaste using scCO₂. The production of fatty acids by scCO₂ extraction is optimized and then compared with other conventional extraction methods such as hexane extraction and the Folch method. The conditions for scCO₂ were temperatures of 313.15K, 323.15K and 333.15K, pressures from 150 bar to 200 bar, and extraction times between 1 and 3 h.

In addition, the extraction of oils from coffee grounds with scCO₂ in the company of green co-solvents such as ethyl lactate was evaluated to see if solvents improve the reaction conditions. It has been shown that the use of co-solvents together with scCO₂ can lead to improvements in oil yields. Therefore in HOOP it will be determined whether this improvement makes the process more sustainable or whether including solvents can be counterproductive from an environmental point of view.

The extracted oil was characterized to quantify fatty acids and analyze its physicochemical properties such as lipid oxidation, antioxidant capacity, moisture content, iodine value, total phenolic content and flavonoid content.

Keywords: Supercritical CO₂, extraction, coffee, valorization.

Biography (150-200 words):

Sergio Clemente is native of Extremadura, and he has studied chemical engineering in Badajoz, Salamanca and Huelva, always with a focus on sustainability and renewable energies, before joining the ITENE team in Valencia in 2024. Since 2020, Sergio has studied and analyzed chemical processes of high temperature chemical recycling, starting with his study of prototypes of polystyrene waste depolymerization plants at the University of Salamanca with a project award. From 2020 to 2023 he has developed his PhD in biofuel production from fast growing biomass at the University of Huelva based on complex kinetic studies and pilot plant producing bio-oil as intermediate biofuel, gas for energetic purpose and biochar applied to agriculture improvers. He is currently developing his professional career as a chemical recycling and valorisation project engineer in ITENE participating in numerous projects with bio-waste, polymers such as PET, polyurethane and other complex polymeric systems such as printed electronics, as well as other wastes such as contaminated wood, bioplastics and functional polyolefins.